

Biological Activities of *Cyperus imbricatus* Retz (Shingle Flat Sedge) Leaf Crude Extract

Kylie Joy P. Tuguinay and Jason Arnold L. Maslang, MBA

Bachelor of Science in Biology

Abstract. *Cyperus imbricatus* Retz. (Shingle Flat Sedge) is traditionally used in Ifugao to treat urinary tract infections. This study determined the biological activities of *C. imbricatus* Retz (shingle flat sedge) leaf crude extract using in vitro assays. Using an experimental design, ethanol-extracted leaf crude was screened for secondary metabolites via Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) and tested for antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic properties through in vitro assays. Phytochemical screening revealed that *C. imbricatus* contains phenols, flavonoids, coumarins, and triterpenes that support the pharmacological potential of *C. imbricatus*. Antimicrobial activity was assessed against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, in which no inhibition was observed. Strong antioxidant activity was observed in the DPPH assay, and strong anti-inflammatory activity in the egg albumin denaturation test. Cytotoxicity, determined via brine shrimp lethality assay, showed high toxicity with an LC₅₀ at a very low concentration. An infographic poster summarizing the findings was shared with local communities to enhance awareness and promote informed use of traditional medicinal plants.

Keywords: Anti-inflammatory activity, antimicrobial activity, antioxidant activity, cytotoxicity, phytochemical screening

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Cyperus imbricatus, commonly known as Shingle flat sedge, is one of the herbal plants prepared by decoction to treat Urinary Tract Infections (Tamayo, 2018). A number of community members of Lamut Ifugao, have claims on the detoxifying activity of the plant. In a review of the phytochemical composition, biological activity, and health-promoting effects of *Cyperus* sp., it was concluded that these species are employed for their medical potential with their plethora of pharmacological attributes such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer (Taheri et al., 2021a). Such biological activities present significant potential for addressing a range of health conditions and enhancing overall well-being (Dar et al., 2023).

While existing studies have extensively explored the biological activities of various species within the *Cyperus* genus, *C. imbricatus* Retz. remained notably understudied. This lack of scientific investigation was particularly evident in relation to its potential antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic properties. Recognizing this gap, the study addressed the scarcity of research on *C. imbricatus* by evaluating its biological activities, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the species and its possible applications in the field of natural product research and drug development.

Statement of the Objectives

The study sought to determine the biological activities of *C. imbricatus* Retz (shingle flat sedge) leaf crude extract using in vitro assays. It was done from January 2024 to May 2025.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the secondary metabolites from the ethanolic extract of *C. imbricatus* leaves?
2. What is the zone of inhibition of the ethanolic extract of *C. imbricatus* leaves against *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*?
3. What is the antioxidant capacity of the crude extract of *C. imbricatus* leaves as measured

- by its ability to reduce DPPH radical activity?
4. What is the efficacy of *C. imbricatus* leaf crude extract in preventing egg albumin protein denaturation, and what does this suggest about anti-inflammatory activity?
 5. What is the effect of *C. imbricatus* leaf crude extract on the viability and metabolic activity of Brine shrimps as determined by Brine shrimp lethality assay?
 6. What Information Education and Communication (IEC) strategy will be employed to inform the residents of Lamut, Ifugao, about the biological activities of *C. imbricatus*?

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed an experimental research design to evaluate the biological activities of the crude extract from *Cyperus imbricatus* Retz. leaves. The extract was obtained through standard procedures involving maceration, filtration, and solvent evaporation. It was subsequently subjected to a series of in vitro bioassays to determine its antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic properties.

Study Site and Sample Collection

This study was conducted at the Center for Natural Sciences (CNS) research laboratory at Saint Mary's University (SMU) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The plant species selected for this study is *C. imbricatus* Retz, which is commonly found in wetland environments, including swamps and marshes. Samples were collected from Lamut, Ifugao. The collection site has been confirmed to be free from known pollution sources, including vehicle emissions, toxic substances, heavy metals, and other contaminants. The samples were gathered prior to air drying, which facilitated subsequent extraction processes.

Specimen Identification

The plant specimen was collected from Lamut, Ifugao and was submitted to the Research Extension and Training (RET) Division of Nueva Vizcaya, State University, for authentication and certification of its botanical or taxonomic identity. The test organisms, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, Brine shrimp eggs were obtained from CNS-SMU.

Data Gathering Procedure

Plant Material Collection and Preparation

Leaves of *C. imbricatus* were collected, washed, and drip-dried. Samples were chopped air-dried, and pulverized using an electric mill.

Crude Extraction of Plant Material

Following Toklo et al. (2023), 400 g of pulverized material was macerated in ethanol for 24 hours. The extract was filtered (Whatman No. 1), evaporated with a rotary evaporator, and refrigerated at 4°C for storage.

Phytochemical Screening via Thin Layer Chromatography

Phytoconstituents were analyzed via TLC (Kalemba et al., 2024) using a 7:3 ethyl acetate chloroform solvent. Extracts were visualized under UV light (254 nm and 365 nm) and treated with reagents per Guevarra et al. (2005).

Antimicrobial Activity Testing

The Kirby-Bauer Method was employed using Mueller-Hinton Broth standardized to 0.5 McFarland (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL). Inoculated agar plates were treated with extract discs and incubated at 35°C for 16–18 hours. Zones of inhibition were measured in mm.

Antioxidant Activity Testing

Using Kalembe et al. (2024), serial dilutions (1.95–1000 µg/mL) of extracts were mixed with 0.02% DPPH solution and incubated for 30 mins at 37°C. Absorbance at 517 nm was recorded, and radical scavenging activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{DPPH Scavenged (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \right) \times 100$$

Anti-inflammatory Activity Assay

Based on Daram et al. (2021), reaction mixtures containing egg albumin, PBS, and varying concentrations of the extract were incubated and heat-treated. Absorbance at 660 nm was used to compute % inhibition of protein denaturation:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \right) \times 100$$

Cytotoxicity Assay

Brine shrimp eggs were hatched in saline for 48 hrs. Extracts (1.95–1000 µg/mL) were tested, and % mortality was assessed after 24 hrs. LC₅₀ values were calculated via Probit analysis in Excel, and classified using the standards of Meyer et al. (1982) and Clarkson et al. (2004).

Treatment of Data

All quantitative data obtained from the bioassays were recorded, tabulated, and statistically analyzed to determine the biological activity of the *Cyperus imbricatus* Retz. Leaf crude extract. Results from the five replicates per treatment in the bioassays, except for the cytotoxicity assay, were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

For the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA), mortality data were used to calculate the median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) using probit analysis. A dose-response curve was plotted, and linear regression was performed to determine the relationship between concentration and mortality rate. Higher LC₅₀ values were interpreted as indicative of lower cytotoxicity and vice versa.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with a reference code number, 2025 0852. Laboratory procedures were conducted under the supervision of the CNS laboratory assistants. The waste materials generated from the study were discarded post-in vitro assay.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Secondary metabolites detected from *C. imbricatus* leaf extract

This section encapsulates the results for the determination of secondary metabolites present in *C. imbricatus* leaf crude extract. The secondary metabolites were detected using the corresponding reagents listed in the first column of the table.

Table 1

Secondary Metabolites from C. imbricatus Extract

Reagent	Compound tested	Result
Preliminary test (H ₂ SO ₄ +heat)	Essential oils	+
	Triterpenes and Sterols	+
Vanillin Sulfuric Acid	Essential oils	-
	Phenols	+
	Fatty acids	+
	All carbohydrates except tetroses and trioses	+
	Anthraquinones	+
Naphthol-sulfuric acid + heat	Coumarins	+
	Anthrones	-
Methanolic potassium hydroxide (KOH-MetOH)	Tannins	+
	Flavonoids	+
Potassium ferricyanide + ferric chloride	Phenols	+
	Alkaloids	-
Dragendorff's reagent	Anthraquinones	+
Magnesium acetate + heat	Amino acid	-

Table 1 presents that the ethanolic extract of *C. imbricatus* leaves was revealed to contain essential oils, triterpenes, sterols, phenols, fatty acids, all carbohydrates except tetroses and trioses, anthraquinones, coumarins, tannins, and flavonoids.

The presence of essential oils, phenolic acids, and flavonoids align with the bioactive compounds found by Peerzada et al. (2015) and Bezerra et al. (2023) from *Cyperus spp.* Additionally, similar results were found in the study of Kumar et al. (2017) on *C. rotundus*, a species in the same genus, which confirmed the presence of carbohydrates, quinones, terpenoids, and coumarins while the study of Zhang et al. (2022) confirmed the presence of tannins and sterols from *C. esculentus*, another species of *Cyperus* genus. These compounds are known to essentially contribute to the bioactivities exhibited by the *C. imbricatus* (Udari, 2018).

Based on the obtained results, *C. imbricatus* is abundant with secondary metabolites that qualify for various biological activities. In light of this, this plant shows potency for pharmacological studies and product formulation.

Section 2. Antimicrobial activity of *C. imbricatus* leaf extract against *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*

This section summarizes the values obtained from Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion. The plant extract and the controls were tested against *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*. In the determination of the ZOI of the plant extract, the Mean \pm SD of the five replicates was recorded in a table.

Table 3

Zone of Inhibition of C. imbricatus against K. pneumoniae and P. aeruginosa

Test substances	ZOI								Result
	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	SD	Mean \pm SD	
<i>C. imbricatus</i> (1000 μ g/mL)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>								Inactive
	7.5	6.8	6	6.2	14.9	8.28	3.746598	8.28 \pm 3.75	
	15.3	12.9	12.3	14.3	12.3	13.42	1.331165	13.42 \pm 1.33	
Streptomycin (+)	6	6	6	6	6	6	0	6	
24% DMSO (-)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>								Inactive
<i>C. imbricatus</i> (1000 μ g/mL)	6	6	6	6	6	6	0	6	
Streptomycin (+)	10.4	10.8	9.3	10.1	10.3	10.18	0.554076	10.18 \pm 0.55	
24% DMSO (-)	6	6	6	6	6	6	0	6	

Table 2 presents the zone of inhibition of the replicates after the extract was introduced to *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*. On *K. pneumoniae*, 1000 µg/mL of *C imbricatus* has a mean inhibiting activity of 8.28mm with a standard deviation of about 3.75mm, which demonstrates inactivity against *K. pneumoniae*. On the other hand, it showed no inhibition on *P. aeruginosa*, thus absolutely inactive.

The *C. Imbricatus* extract contained essential oils, fatty acids, triterpenes, sterols, coumarins, and anthraquinones. These non-polar compounds were found to exhibit antimicrobial activity (Burt, 2004, as cited by Falleh et al., 2020; Sonkoue et al., 2023; Arellano et al., 2023; Smyth et al., 2009, as cited by Hassanein et al., 2020; Qun et al., 2023). The little to no inhibition of the extract in the disk diffusion method may have been attributed to the poor diffusion of non-polar compounds into the MHA (Bubonja-Ssonje et al., 2020). Moreover, the poor solubility of essential oils found in this plant poses a major limitation, particularly when incorporating the extract into the media. This drawback significantly reduced their antimicrobial efficacy in practical applications (Gyawali & Ibrahim, 2014).

Based on the mean ZOI against the bacteria, *C. imbricatus* demonstrated no inhibitory activity on *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*. This implies that the plant extract has no potential as an antimicrobial agent for UTI and thus suggests that its effect on UTI patients may not be attributable to this biological activity.

Section 3. Scavenging activity of the *C. imbricatus* extract to neutralize DPPH radicals.

This section presents the scavenging activity of *C. imbricatus* to neutralize DPPH radicals. The result was presented through a bar graph, highlighting the mean % inhibition of the different concentrations of the plant against DPPH radicals. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 1

Inhibitory Activity of C. imbricatus against DPPH Radicals

Figure 1 shows a chart of the scavenging activity of *C. imbricatus* against DPPH radicals. The graph illustrates the antioxidant activity of the plant at concentrations ranging from 1000- 1.95 µg/mL. The highest concentration has the lowest antioxidant activity, reaching a mean inhibition of 28.52%. In contrast, the lowest concentration has the highest antioxidant activity, reaching a mean inhibition of 65%, approaching the inhibitory activity of Ascorbic, which is 75% at 1.95 µg/mL. The negative control shows minimal to no activity, confirming that the observed results are attributable to the extract. The chart clearly shows an increasing trend of scavenging activity as the

concentration decreases (from 1000 ug/mL down to 1.95 ug/mL). This indicates a dose-dependent effect, where lower concentrations of the extract exhibit stronger radical scavenging activity within the tested range.

This strong antioxidant activity of *C. imbricatus* is comparable to the antioxidant activity of the *Cyperus spp.* studied by Bezerra et al. (2023) and Taheri et al. (2021), showing high antioxidant properties. However, the relationship between concentration and activity is observably inversely proportional in this study, in which the lower the concentration of *C. imbricatus* extract, the higher the antioxidant activity is and vice versa. As cited by Chaves et al. (2020) from the study of Li et al. (2014), the antioxidant capacity of phenols in plant extracts is generally effective at low concentrations.

Therefore, the ability of *C. imbricatus* extract to scavenge DPPH radicals is most effective at low concentrations due to its phenolic content, as shown in Section 1. This implies that the plant is high in antioxidant properties, making the plant essential in neutralizing free radicals that cause various diseases by cell damage, thus improving immune function. Moreover, it can be utilized in the formulation of pharmacological products, food supplements, cosmetics, and preservatives.

Section 4. Anti-inflammatory activity of *C. imbricatus* against protein denaturation

This section presents the inhibitory activity of *C. imbricatus* against the denaturation of egg albumin caused by heat. The mean percentage of the activity per concentration of the extract is represented in Figure 5. The error bars describe the significance of the statistical differences of the mean.

Figure 2

Inhibitory activity of C. imbricatus against egg albumin denaturation

Figure 2 illustrates the ability of *C. imbricatus* extract to inhibit protein denaturation after the egg albumin has been exposed to heat. The chart demonstrates that the crude extract possesses the ability to inhibit protein denaturation in a concentration-dependent manner. The optimal concentration for this activity appears to be around 31.25 ug/mL, achieving 79.33% inhibition. In comparison, its MIC is observed at 1.95 ug/mL. While the inhibition generally increases as the concentration decreases from 1000 ug/mL to this optimal point, concentrations lower than 31.25 ug/mL showed reduced efficacy. The generally short error bars indicate good precision in the experimental measurements, allowing for confidence in the observed trends and the identification of concentrations with significantly different inhibitory effects.

Previous studies on *Cyperus* presented bioactivities of plant species belonging to the genus, including anti-inflammatory activity (Bezerra et al., 2022). This biological activity is concluded by Pratiwi et al. (2024) to be attributable to the detected secondary metabolites, such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, sterols, and triterpenes, which are detected in the plant as shown in Section 1. The synergism of these compounds, which are generally found in medicinal plants such as *C. imbricatus*, exhibit pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory activity (Gonfa et al., 2023). Moreover, polysaccharides are carbohydrates that play a significant role in immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory activity (Elbandy, 2022).

Based on the data and related studies, *C. imbricatus* exhibits promising anti-inflammatory activity, especially at the identified optimal concentration, as determined by its ability to reduce the denaturation of egg albumin. While the immune system functions to protect the body from infection by inflammation, uncontrolled inflammation leads to cell and tissue damage, which can be fatal. The plant's anti-inflammatory activity is crucial to reducing uncontrolled inflammation, thus its crucial role in immune function.

Section 5. Cytotoxic activity of *C. imbricatus* on brine shrimps

This section shows a dose-response curve showing the cytotoxicity of *C. imbricatus*. The X-axis indicates varying concentrations of the *C. imbricatus* extract. In contrast, the Y-axis indicates the mean percentage of cell mortality at each concentration. The data was analyzed using probit analysis, and a linear regression chart was used to present the LC50.

Figure 3

Cytotoxicity of C. imbricatus to Nauplii Brine Shrimps

Note. Data points show the mean % mortality at each concentration. The red mark indicates the LC₅₀ and the regression line illustrates the dose-response relationship between extract concentration and mortality.

Figure 3 shows the mean mortality rate of nauplii brine shrimp after it has been exposed to the different concentrations of *C. imbricatus* extract. The lethal concentration that caused 50% mortality (LC₅₀) to the nauplii brine shrimps was 95.66 µg/mL as determined using Probit analysis and regression formula. Using the classification of toxicity in Table 1, the plant is considered highly toxic.

Based on the results obtained from the phytochemical screening, as presented in Section 1, *C. imbricatus* extract was positive for Tannins. In the study of Younus et al. (2021), it was suggested that Tannins may have cytotoxic activity. It was further proven that this secondary metabolite exhibits a substantial cytotoxic effect against tumor cells due to a specific Tannin called Corilagin (Jit et al., 2024). In the study of Chudzik et al. (2015), as cited by David et al. (2024), triterpenes were proven to have anticancer and chemo preventive properties and to induce cancer cell apoptosis without damaging the normal cells. Abotaleb et al. (2020) also studied polyphenols, such

as tannins and flavonoids, which exhibit cell proliferation reduction and apoptosis. In addition, coumarins exhibit similar activity (Rawat & Reddy, 2022).

Therefore, *C. imbricatus* extract is proven to exhibit cytotoxic effects on nauplii brine shrimps due to the presence of cytotoxic compounds like triterpenes, phenols, and coumarins. This bioactivity sets its qualification as a cytotoxic agent that combat cancer cell proliferation. However, this study also suggests caution for oral intake due to its highly toxic nature. This also supports the caution advised by the users on the dosage and frequency of consumption due to its possible side effects.

Section 6. Information Education and Communication

This section presents the IEC material used to disseminate the results of this study. Scientific data were summarized and translated for better understanding among the community. It was submitted to the barangay officials with the attached transmittal letter for approval.

Figure 4

Infographics on The Biological Activities of C. imbricatus

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES
Cyperus imbricatus (SHINGGLE FLATSEDGE)

C. imbricatus is locally known as **obod-obod, ballayang, balabalongutan, and falili**, that thrives in both irrigated and rainfed lowland rice fields. It is one of the herbal plants, prepared by decoction to treat Urinary Tract Infection (Tamayo, 2018).

Secondary metabolites

- Essential oils
- Triterpenes and Sterols
- Essential oils
- Phenols
- Fatty acids
- All carbohydrates except tetroses and trioses
- Antraquinones
- Coumarins
- Anthrone
- Tannins
- Flavonoids
- Phenols
- Alkaloids
- Antraquinones
- Amino acid

C. imbricatus underwent through antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and cytotoxicity testing

Based on the results obtained, *C. imbricatus* were confirmed to have:

- ➔ **Antimicrobial Activity Inactive**
The plant extract did not show any activity to fight UTI-causing bacteria in the test.
- ➔ **Antioxidant Activity Highly active**
This plant helps keep your cells safe from harmful substances that speed up aging or lead to disease
- ➔ **Anti-inflammatory Activity Highly active**
The extract can calm down swelling, pain, or redness in the body
- ➔ **Cytotoxicity Highly active**
The plant extract can kill or damage harmful cells, such as cancer cells

This study suggests caution for oral intake due to its highly toxic nature. This also supports the caution advised by the users on the dosage and frequency of consumption due its possible side effects.

Authors:
Kylie Joy P. Tuguinay (Researcher)
Jason L. Maslang (Adviser-Promoter)

For more information,
Contact: 09183714497

Figure 4 shows an infographic poster containing the biological activities of *C. imbricatus*. It presents the results obtained and interpreted in the previous sections, such as its secondary metabolites, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic activity of the plant. This IEC material serves as a means to spread awareness about the bioactivities of this plant, especially the need for caution on its cytotoxic tendency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

This study determined the biological activities of *C. imbricatus* leaf crude extract, namely, its antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic activity. The result of the phytochemical screening revealed that *C. imbricatus* leaf ethanolic extract contained essential oils, triterpenes and sterols, phenols, fatty acids, all carbohydrates except tetroses and trioses, antraquinones, coumarins, tannins, and flavonoids. It was also tested for its antimicrobial activity, and it showed no zones of inhibition against *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*. While the antimicrobial assay obtained negative results, it showed high antioxidant and anti-inflammatory

activity at low concentrations. It was found to be highly toxic as its LC50 against nauplii brine shrimps was determined at a low concentration. However, its level of toxicity suggests caution before consumption. The results were disseminated in the community in order to spread awareness on the biological activities, as well as caution on its consumption.

Recommendations

Based on the obtained results of this study, the following are recommended:

1. Determine the RF value of the secondary metabolites to identify organic compounds and chemical reactions and purifications.
2. Further exploration of the bioactivities, in vitro and in vivo, of *C. imbricatus* extract is needed to provide a stronger scientific foundation.
3. Determine the *C. imbricatus* extract's cytotoxicity through molecular diagnostic tests to determine the extent of its cytotoxicity.
4. Conduct an ethnopharmacological and translational toxicology study aimed at developing an evidence-based health policy for the safe use of a traditionally utilized medicinal plant.

References

- Abotaleb, M., Liskova, A., Kubatka, P., & Busselberg, D. (2020). Therapeutic potential of plant phenolic acids in the treatment of cancer. *Biomolecules*, 10(2), 221. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10020221>
- Arellano, H., Nardello-Rataj, V., Szunerits, S., Boukherroub, R., & Fameau, A. (2023). Saturated long chain fatty acids as possible natural alternative antibacterial agents: Opportunities and challenges. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, 318, 102952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2023.102952>
- Bezerra, J. J. L., Feitosa, B. F., Souto, P. C., & Pinheiro, A. a. V. (2023). *Cyperus esculentus* L. (Cyperaceae): Agronomic aspects, food applications, ethnomedicinal uses, biological activities, phytochemistry and toxicity. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 47, 102606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2023.102606>
- Bezerra, J. J. L., Pinheiro, A. a. V., & De Oliveira, A. F. M. (2022). Cyperaceae species used for the treatment of inflammation: A review of ethnomedicinal, pharmacological, toxicological, and phytochemical evidence. *South African Journal of Botany*, 150, 1138–1158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2022.09.020>
- Burt, S. (2004). Essential oils: their antibacterial properties and potential applications in foods—a review. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 94(3), 223–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2004.03.022>
- Chudzik, M., Korzonek-Szlacheta, I., & Krol, W. (2015). Triterpenes as potentially cytotoxic compounds. *Molecules*, 20(1), 1610–1625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules20011610>
- Daram, P., Jitta, S. R., Shreedhara, C., Misra, C. S., Gourishetti, K., & Lobo, R. (2021b). Investigation of anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritis potentials of Terminalia catappa bark using in vitro assays and carrageenan-induced inflammation, complete Freund's adjuvant-induced arthritis model in rats. *South African Journal of Botany*, 141, 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2021.05.010>

- Dar, R. A., Shahnawaz, M., Ahanger, M. A., & Majid, I. U. (2023). Exploring the Diverse Bioactive Compounds from Medicinal Plants: A Review. *The Journal of Phytopharmacology*, 12(3), 189–195. <https://doi.org/10.31254/phyto.2023.12307>
- David, S. I., Danborn, B., & Bauchi, Z. (2024). Anticancer Effect of Aqueous and Ethanol Extract of Pepperfruit (*Dennettia tripetala*) fruit on MCF-7 Breast Cancer Cell Line using Neutral Red Uptake Assay. *Biological Sciences*, 04(04). <https://doi.org/10.55006/biolsciences.2024.4402>
- Elbandy, M. (2022). Anti-inflammatory effects of marine bioactive compounds and their potential as functional food ingredients in the prevention and treatment of neuroinflammatory disorders. *Molecules*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28010002>
- Falleh, H., Jemaa, M. B., Saada, M., & Ksouri, R. (2020). Essential oils: A promising eco-friendly food preservative. *Food Chemistry*, 330, 127268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127268>
- Gonfa, Y. H., Tessema, F. B., Bachheti, A., Rai, N., Tadesse, M. G., Singab, A. N., Chaubey, K. K., & Bachheti, R. K. (2023). Anti-inflammatory activity of phytochemicals from medicinal plants and their nanoparticles: A review. *Current Research in Biotechnology*, 6, 100152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbiot.2023.100152>
- Hassanein, E. H. M., Sayed, A. M., Hussein, O. E., & Mahmoud, A. M. (2020). Coumarins as modulators of the KEAP1/NRF2/ARE signaling pathway. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2020, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1675957>
- Jit, T., Roy, S. D., Shil, D., Chakraborty, J., Paul, A., Roy, S., & De, D. (2024). The potential of tannins from medicinal plants as anticancer agents. www.plantsjournal.com. <https://www.plantsjournal.com/archives/?year=2024&vol=12&issue=4&part=E&ArticleId=1735>
- Kalemba, M. R. K., Makhuvele, R., & Njobeh, P. B. (2024). Phytochemical screening, the antioxidant activity of selected methanolic plant extracts, and their detoxification capabilities against AFB1 toxicity. *Heliyon*, 10(2), e24435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24435>
- Rawat, A., & Reddy, A. V. B. (2022). Recent advances on anticancer activity of coumarin derivatives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry Reports*, 5, 100038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmcr.2022.100038>
- Smyth, T., Ramachandran, V., & Smyth, W. (2009). A study of the antimicrobial activity of selected naturally occurring and synthetic coumarins. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 33(5), 421–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2008.10.022>
- Sonkoue, A. M., Kengne, I. C., Lacmata, S. T., Ngnokam, C. D. J., Djamalladine, M. D., Voutquenne-Nazabadioko, L., Ngnokam, D., & Tamokou, J. (2023). Triterpene and Steroids from *Ludwigia abyssinica* A. Rich (Onagraceae) Displayed Antimicrobial Activities and Synergistic Effects with Conventional Antibiotics. *Evidence-based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2023, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/2975909>
- Taheri, Y., Herrera-Bravo, J., Huala, L., Salazar, L. A., Sharifi-Rad, J., Akram, M., Shahzad, K., Melgar-Lalanne, G., Baghalpour, N., Tamimi, K., Mahroo-Bakhtiyari, J., Kregiel, D., Dey, A., Kumar, M., Suleria, H. a. R., Cruz-Martins, N., & Cho, W. C. (2021). *Cyperus* spp.: A Review of Phytochemical Composition, Biological Activity, and Health-Promoting Effects. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2021, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4014867>

- Tamayo, P. a. A. (2018). Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used by the Ayangans of Ifugao, Philippines. *Advanced Science Letters*, 24(10), 7047–7052. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2018.12405>
- Toklo, P. M., Challaton, K. P., Assogba, M. F., Akakpo, G. A., Kifouly, A. H., Alowanou, G. G., Hounzangbe-Adote, S., Yayi, E. C., & Gbenou, J. D. (2023). Phytochemical screening, in vitro and in vivo effects of an aqueous extract of the bark of *Combretum glutinosum* Perr ex DC. (Combretaceae) on gastrointestinal strongyles. *Phytomedicine Plus*, 3(4), 100491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2023.100491>
- Udari, L. (2018). Medicinal properties of *Cyperus* species (Sedge family, Cyperaceae). [https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Medicinal-Properties-of-Cyperus-Species-\(Sedge-Udari/58c2e24e359ca4c49fea9f03f6af3f8270400cde](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Medicinal-Properties-of-Cyperus-Species-(Sedge-Udari/58c2e24e359ca4c49fea9f03f6af3f8270400cde)
- Younus, M., Hasan, M., Hanif, M., Sarwar, G., Ahmad, K., Ur Rehman, S., Shirazi, J., Jamil, Q., Khan, K., Syed, S., Ghaffari, A., Khan, M., Abdullah, M., Wazir, M., & Rehman, A. (2021). Botanical Features and Anti-cancerous Potential of *Euphorbia nivulia* Buch.-Ham. *Tropical Journal of Natural Product Research*, 5(9), 1591–1596. <https://doi.org/10.26538/tjnpr/v5i9.11>